

EFFECTS OF VIDEO LESSONS ON THE ATTRIBUTES AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 7 LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

This study sought the effects of video lessons on the attributes (attitude, anxiety, motivation, and engagement) and academic performance of Grade 7 learners in Marinduque National High School. The researcher used a descriptive quasi-experimental design with two comparative groups of learners: the control and experimental groups. In the experimental group, lessons were taught through video lessons, whereas in the control group, traditional method of teaching is applied. The effects of video lessons on students' academic performance in mathematics were examined by comparing the control group's Mean Percentage Score (MPS) to that of the experimental group. While the effects of video lessons on students' attributes were examined by comparing the mean scores in four standardized tests obtained before and after integrating video lessons into the teaching-learning process. An independent sample t-test was employed to determine the significance of any differences in academic performance and level of attributes between the two groups. The research findings indicate that video lessons were more effective in improving students' academic performance in mathematics than traditional teaching methods. Video lessons can enhance academic performance, especially for representing/illustrating geometric concepts. Video lessons also have been shown to improve student anxiety, engagement, and motivation. The study recommends introducing video lessons into Mathematics classes alongside traditional teaching techniques, particularly for visual/concrete representations. Furthermore, the researcher suggested investigating additional studies about the long-term effects of video lessons on academic performance and student attitudes, with larger sample sizes across different grade levels and a more extended experimentation period.

Keywords: *academic performance, anxiety, attitude, engagement, motivation, video lessons*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics educators across all levels of education share a common objective: to help students understand mathematical concepts better. Mastery of mathematical ideas is not just crucial for academic achievement but also for navigating daily tasks efficiently. Several factors contribute to molding the comprehension and acquisition of mathematical concepts. These include motivation of students to learn, engagement in the teaching-learning process, anxiety towards the subject mathematics, and attitude towards this subject.

Unfortunately, many students have negative mathematical experiences that start in elementary school, affecting their perspective on mathematics. (Graven, 2015). Mathematics is one of the subjects that many students dislike. Many students consider Mathematics the most challenging and dreaded subject in the country's K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum. It is not because students lack competence but because they have a negative attitude toward mathematics (Kusmaryono et al., 2019). When confronted with arithmetic problems, most students get fearful and uneasy. Some even try to avoid this subject because it is the most challenging. As a result, students experience anxiety when faced with a mathematical challenge. Mathematical anxiety was consistently proven to correlate negatively with students' performance in mathematics. (Ho et al., 2000).

The researcher has witnessed the academic struggles of students in Mathematics while teaching in public secondary schools. The researcher has been teaching in public secondary schools for three years and has seen how pupils score poorly in math.

Results on national and international learning scale assessments in Mathematics showed that the Philippines has consistently performed poorly. According to the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) results, the Philippines placed second to last in Mathematics based on country means (Department of Education, 2019). For the second time, the Philippines ranked in the bottom ten among 81 countries in reading comprehension, mathematics, and science according to the most current 2022 PISA data. According to the 2019 Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) evaluation, the Philippines ranked last in Mathematics among 58 countries, with a score of 297. While the Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics 2019 (SEA-PLM) revealed that only seventeen percent (17%) of Filipino Grade 5 students met the minimal mathematics standard expected at the end of primary school as outlined in Sustainable Development Goals SDG 4.1.1 - Education Proficiency. On the other hand, the Department of Education (DepEd) has given the National Achievement Test (NAT) to students in public schools nationwide, particularly in Grades 6, 10, and 12. The performance of Grade 6, 10, and 12 pupils in Mathematics is concerning, as the NAT results for the school years 2016-2017, 2017-2018, and 2018-2019 were worse than the NAT results of the previous school years.

The above scenario shows that Filipino learners have consistently performed poorly in Mathematics along several national and international learning scale assessments. These results showed that many students in the Philippines need help in Mathematics.

The Department of Education launched a project to incorporate technological innovations into the classroom to assist students in understanding and learning more effectively and improve educational quality. In general, traditional educational methodologies have proven unable to keep up with quickly evolving technology and environmental changes (Ayçiçek, 2018). Teachers used numerous strategies to address these difficulties to improve student engagement with content and classroom involvement using digital devices in the classroom (Klette et al., 2018).

The Department of Education saw the need to adapt video-based materials and engaging services to support the learning aids required by students and teachers during the teaching and learning process. As part of information and communication technology, the Philippines viewed instructional videos as a growing means that have become a popular way to learn inside and outside the classroom. They can be helpful for effective and quality learning for students' academic growth and performance. Furthermore, several recent advancements, most notably the rapid expansion of access to high-speed Internet via homes, schools, and personal devices such as tablets or smartphones, have significantly impacted the learning environment and hastened video use in education, particularly in Eastern countries.

Using videos for learning enhanced teachers' teaching productivity, with videos providing the most satisfaction (Tang & Austin, 2009). There have been various studies on the impact of video lessons on the education sector; however, there is a lack of research on the effects of video lessons on students' academic performance and attributes.

Given the preceding scenario, the researcher believes that it is necessary to investigate the impact of video lessons as a teaching tool on students' attributes and academic performance in Mathematics.

Research Questions

Due to the above scenario, based on personal observations made by the researcher and previous studies concerning the issues and solutions presented, she had come up with this thematic interest: What are the effects of video lessons in improving mathematical attributes and academic performance of Grade 7 students?

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the student's level of academic performance of the control and experimental groups in mathematics in the following competencies:
 - 1.1. The learner represents point, line, and plane using concrete and pictorial models;
 - 1.2. The learner illustrates subsets of a line;
 - 1.3. The learner classifies the different kinds of angles;

- 1.4. The learner derives relationships of geometric figures using measurement and inductive reasoning: supplementary angles, complementary angles, congruent angles, vertical angles, adjacent angles, and linear pairs;
- 1.5. The learner derives relationships of geometric figures using measurement and inductive reasoning: intersecting lines, perpendicular lines, parallel lines, and skew lines;
- 1.6. The learner derives relationships among angles formed by parallel lines cut by a transversal using measurement and inductive reasoning;
- 1.7. The learner illustrates polygons: (a) convexity, (b) angles, and (c) sides;
- 1.8. The learner derives inductively the relationship of the exterior and interior angles of a convex polygon;
- 1.9. The learner illustrates a circle and the terms related to it: radius, diameter chord, center, arc, chord, central angles, and inscribed angles; and
- 1.10. The learner solves problems involving the sides and angles of a polygon.
2. Is there a significant difference between the post-tests of the control group and experimental groups?
3. What are the students' level attributes towards Mathematics in the control and experimental groups in terms of the following:
 - 3.1. level of attitude;
 - 3.2. anxiety level;
 - 3.3. level of motivation;
 - 3.4. level of engagement?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of students' attributes towards mathematics before and after the intervention on the control and experimental groups in terms of the following:
 - 4.1. level of attitude
 - 4.2. anxiety level
 - 4.3. level of motivation
 - 4.4. level of engagement?
5. What video-based teaching package can be proposed based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

To develop a comprehensive study, the researcher adopted the descriptive quasi-experimental design. The researcher used two groups of students for the study. The descriptive analysis described the level of students' attributes and academic performance towards mathematics. At the same time, the quasi-experimental design determined the effects of video lessons in improving the mathematical attributes of students.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in Marinduque, an island province in the Philippines located in the Southwestern Tagalog Region or MIMAROPA, formerly Region IV-B. The province of Marinduque is considered the geographical center of the Philippines by the Luzon Datum of 1911, the mother of all Philippine geodetic surveys. Its capital is the municipality of Boac, where Marinduque National High School is located. Furthermore, Boac, Marinduque is the province's most populous town and continues to be the hub of industry, culture, business, and education.

Marinduque National High School, or MNHS for short, is a public secondary school in Isok I, Boac, Marinduque, founded in 1914. It is acknowledged as the province's first secondary school. At present, there are 3414 junior high school students at Marinduque National High School; 1733 are male, and 1681 are female.

Research Population and Sample

The study's sample included officially enrolled students from two Grade 7 sections that the researcher is currently handling for the school year 2023-2024. The researcher used a purposive sampling method. All Grade 7 students were given diagnostic test at the beginning of the third quarter and the results were summarized using mean percentage scores. Two sections with similar or adjacent MPS were selected. These two sections are Grade 7 – Aquarius and Grade 7 – Scorpio composed of 49 students with 15 males and 34 females, and 48 students with 19 males and 29 females respectively. The Grade 7 – Aquarius section served as the experimental group and the Grade 7 – Scorpio section served as the control group.

Research Instrument

The researcher utilized, adapted, and modified the following research instruments needed to obtain the necessary data for the study:

The researcher used the Attitudes Toward Mathematics Inventory (ATMI) by Tapia (2004), which consists of 40 items designed to assess high school students' attitudes toward mathematics. Twenty-nine (29) pieces contain favorable written sentiments on mathematics, whereas eleven (11) are unfavorable. ATMI employs a five-point Likert scale with responses ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree (Tapia, 2004). The assessment has four categories: enjoyment, motivation, self-confidence, and value.

The first category consists of ten statements that measure enjoyment. This category assesses how much students enjoy the subject and the process of working with mathematics (Tapia & Marsh, 2004). The second category consists of five statements that measure motivation. These statements assess a student's interest in mathematics and the likelihood of continuing to study it (Tapia & Marsh, 2004). The third category consists of 15 statements that assess self-confidence. These statements assess students' feelings about mathematics in a course and when working on mathematics

(Tapia & Marsh, 2004). In this area, a learner assesses sentiments while thinking about and working on mathematics. The fourth category consists of ten statements that measure value. These statements measure the level at which a student believes mathematics is helpful to them (Tapia & Marsh, 2004).

In measuring the anxiety level of the students towards Mathematics, the researcher adapted and modified the Mathematical Anxiety Scale Instrument for Junior High School students by Anindyarini and Supahar (2019), where questionnaires were developed based on Stuart and Sunden's theory of anxiety. The 35-item questionnaire has the symptoms of anxiety shown by students, which can be physiological, behavioral, cognitive, and affective responses.

To assess students' anxiety levels regarding mathematics, the researcher adapted and modified Anindyarini and Supahar's (2019) Mathematical Anxiety Scale Instrument for Junior High School students, which includes questionnaires based on Stuart and Sunden's anxiety theory. The 35-item questionnaire includes the symptoms of anxiety displayed by students, which can be physiological, behavioral, cognitive, or affective responses.

In measuring students' engagement levels, the researcher modified the student engagement scale by Quiñones Pareja (2009). The student engagement scale includes behavioral, affective, and cognitive domains and five target factors: class participation, relationship with faculty and staff, interaction with peers, participation in school events, and use of school resources.

The researcher designed several pre-tests and post-tests to measure the student's academic performance. The pre-tests and post-tests assessed the third-quarter competencies in Mathematics 7.

To test the validity of the research instruments, the researcher submitted it to experts to check the completeness and appropriateness of the questionnaire. The research instruments that measure the different attributes were slightly modified to fit the reading and comprehension levels of Grade 7 students. One modification is replacing some vocabulary words with more basic terminologies. Moreover, the researcher restructured the pre-and post-tests to make an equal number of items in each learning competency between pre-and post-tests. The researcher also restructured the questions in the pre-and post-tests in a paralleled way.

Data Gathering Procedures

To uphold ethics and ensure the respondents' full collaboration, the researcher first sought authorization from the Superintendent of Schools Division of Marinduque through an official letter. Following clearance, the researcher requested authorization from the principal of Marinduque National High School to formally perform the study. Finally, the researcher explained the study's objectives to the students.

The researcher used the adapted and modified research instruments to administer a pre-and post-assessment to both the control and experimental groups at the beginning and end of the third quarter of the school year 2023-2024 to determine the level of attitude, level of anxiety, level of motivation, and level of engagement toward Mathematics. On the other hand, the quarterly pre-test and quarterly assessment results determine the academic performance in mathematics before and after employing video lessons.

The experimental group learned the third quarter lessons with video assistance, whereas the control group covered the lessons through traditional methods without video support.

Assessment of various variables occurred within specific time intervals:

1. Pre-assessment of the level of attributes before the start of the third quarter.
2. Post-assessment of the level of attributes at the end of the third quarter.
3. Quarterly Assessment at the end of the quarter.
4. The schedule of formative assessments with the covered learning competencies is as follows:

Table 1

Learning Competencies in Third Quarter Mathematics 7 with the corresponding schedule of formative assessments

Week No.	Learning Competencies The learner....	Formative Assessments
Week 1	represents point, line, and plane using concrete and pictorial models. illustrates subsets of a line. classifies the different kinds of angles.	Formative Assessment 1
Week 2	derives relationships of geometric figures using measurement and inductive reasoning: supplementary angles, complementary angles, congruent angles, vertical angles, adjacent angles, and linear pairs. derives relationships of geometric figures using measurement and inductive reasoning: intersecting lines, perpendicular lines, parallel lines, and skew lines.	Formative Assessment 2
Week 3	derives relationships among angles formed by parallel lines cut by a transversal using measurement and inductive reasoning.	Formative Assessment 3
Week 4	illustrates polygons: (a) convexity; (b) angles; and (c) sides. derives inductively the relationship of the exterior and interior angles of a convex polygon.	Formative Assessment 4
Week 5	illustrates a circle and the terms related to it: radius, diameter chord, center, arc, chord, central angle, and inscribed angle. solves problems involving the sides and angles of a polygon.	Formative Assessment 5

The researcher recorded, tallied, computed, tabulated/graphed, analyzed, and interpreted all the gathered data.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The statistical tests used in the study include a) Arithmetic mean, b) Mean Percentage Score, c) Independent samples t-test, and d) Paired samples t-test.

The Arithmetic Mean was used to determine the level of mathematical attributes in the population across a weekly time frame. The following range of values were utilized, along with their descriptive interpretations.

Table 2***Descriptive Interpretation of the Students' Level of Attitude towards Mathematics***

Range of Means	Descriptive Interpretation
4.21 – 5.00	Students' level of attitude towards Mathematics is Highly Positive
3.41 – 4.20	Students' level of attitude towards Mathematics is Moderately Positive
2.61 – 3.40	Students' level of attitude towards Mathematics is Positive
1.81 – 2.60	Students' level of attitude towards Mathematics is Negative
1.00 – 1.80	Students' level of attitude towards Mathematics is Extremely Negative

Table 3***Descriptive Interpretation of the Students' Level of Motivation in Mathematics***

Range of Means	Descriptive Interpretation
4.21 – 5.00	Students' level of motivation towards Mathematics is Highly Positive
3.41 – 4.20	Students' level of motivation towards Mathematics is Moderately Positive
2.61 – 3.40	Students' level of motivation towards Mathematics is Positive
1.81 – 2.60	Students' level of motivation towards Mathematics is Negative
1.00 – 1.80	Students' level of motivation towards Mathematics is Extremely Negative

Table 4***Descriptive Interpretation of Student's Mathematical Anxiety in Mathematics***

Range of Means	Descriptive Interpretation
4.21 – 5.00	Students' level of Mathematics anxiety is Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Students' level of Mathematics anxiety is Moderately High
2.61 – 3.40	Students' level of Mathematics anxiety is High
1.81 – 2.60	Students' level of Mathematics anxiety is Low
1.00 – 1.80	Students' level of Mathematics anxiety is Very Low

Table 5***Descriptive Interpretation of the Students' Level of Engagement in Mathematics***

Range of Means	Descriptive Interpretation
4.21 – 5.00	Students' level of engagement in class is Highly Positive
3.41 – 4.20	Students' level of engagement in class is Moderately Positive
2.61 – 3.40	Students' level of engagement in class is Positive
1.81 – 2.60	Students' level of engagement in class is Negative
1.00 – 1.80	Students' level of engagement in class is Extremely Negative

The mean percentage scores determine the pupils' academic performance before and after the intervention. The following range of values were utilized, along with their descriptive interpretations.

Table 6***Descriptive Interpretation of the Mean Percentage Score***

Mean Percentage Score	Descriptive Interpretation
60 and below	Low Mastery
61 – 79	Moving Towards Mastery
80 above	Mastered

The significance of any observed variations in post-test scores between the control and experimental groups was determined using an independent samples t-test. The same statistical method determined the significant difference in post-assessment scores for the various academic attributes between the control and experimental groups.

A paired samples t-test determined the significance of any observed differences between the pre-assessment and post-assessment of the different academic attributes of the experimental group.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study focused on the effects of using video lessons on the attributes and academic performance of Grade 7 students. The different attributes to be measured are attitude toward Mathematics, anxiety, academic motivation, and academic engagement.

The respondents of this study were the two Grade 7 sections where the researcher is currently teaching for the school year 2023-2024. These sections were composed of control and experimental groups. The time frame for conducting the study was only limited to the third quarter period of the SY 2023-2024.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Academic Performance of the Control and Experimental Groups in Mathematics

The student's academic performance levels in Mathematics were measured using the mean percentage score (MPS) in the pre-tests and post-tests of the control and experimental groups. The student's academic performance level was analyzed to compare the effect of using video lessons in the experimental group to the effect of using traditional teaching methods in the control group. The total number of respondents in the control group is 48 students, while there are 49 in the experimental group. The generated data is in matrix form. The succeeding Table 7, Table 8, and Table 9 summarize the data gathered from the students.

1.1. Level of Academic Performance of the Control and Experimental Groups Using Pre-tests

Table 7

Mean Percentage Score of the Pre-tests in the Control and Experimental Groups according to Third Quarter Competencies in Mathematics 7

Competencies	Control Group		Experimental Group		MD
	MPS	I	MPS	I	
1. represents point, line, and plane using concrete and pictorial models	43.88	LM	50.06	LM	-6.18
2. illustrates subsets of a line					
3. classifies the different kinds of angles					
4. derives relationships of geometric figures using measurement and inductive reasoning: supplementary angles, complementary angles, congruent angles, vertical angles, adjacent angles, and linear pairs	32.82	LM	36.17	LM	-3.35
5. derives relationships of geometric figures using measurement and inductive reasoning: intersecting lines, perpendicular lines, parallel lines, and skew lines	40.30	LM	41.90	LM	-1.60
6. derives relationships among angles formed by parallel lines cut by a transversal using measurement and inductive reasoning.					

7. illustrates polygons: (a) convexity; (b) angles; and (c)sides.					
8. derives inductively the relationship of the exterior and interior angles of a convex polygon.	31.23	LM	43.52	LM	-12.29
9. illustrates a circle and the terms related to it: radius, diameter chord, center, arc, chord, central angles, and inscribed angles.	34.49	LM	58.03	LM	-23.54
10. solve problems involving the sides and angles of a polygon					
Mean of Pre-tests	36.54	LM	45.94	LM	-9.40
Third Quarter Diagnostic Test	34.10	LM	34.65	LM	-0.55

Legend: MPS – Mean Percentage Score, I – Interpretation, MD – Mean Difference
LM – Low Mastery, MTM – Moving Towards Mastery, M – Mastered

Table 7 above shows the mean percentage scores (MPS) of the pre-tests in different learning competencies conducted weekly on the control and experimental groups. The MPS of the experimental group is higher than the MPS of the control group in almost all of the learning competencies. However, it is noticeable that the result of the MPS in the initial third quarter diagnostic test varied less. The control group had an MPS of 34.10, and the experimental group had an MPS of 34.65. The initial result of the third quarter diagnostic test served as the determining factor in choosing the control and experimental groups.

1.2. Level of Academic Performance of the Control and Experimental Groups Using Post-tests

Table 8

Mean Percentage Score of the Post-tests in the Control and Experimental Groups according to Third Quarter Competencies in Mathematics 7

Competencies	Control Group		Experimental Group		MD
	MPS	I	MPS	I	
1. represents point, line, and plane using concrete and pictorial models	59.03	LM	70.67	MTM	-11.64
2. illustrates subsets of a line					
3. classifies the different kinds of angles					
4. derives relationships of geometric figures using measurement and inductive reasoning: supplementary angles, complementary angles, congruent angles, vertical angles, adjacent angles, and linear pairs	67.87	MTM	68.85	MTM	-0.98
5. derives relationships of geometric figures using measurement and inductive reasoning: intersecting lines, perpendicular lines, parallel lines, and skew lines	55.04	LM	58.79	LM	-3.75
6. derives relationships among angles formed by parallel lines cut by a transversal using measurement and inductive reasoning.					
7. illustrates polygons: (a) convexity; (b) angles; and (c)sides.	41.91	LM	59.12	LM	-17.21
8. derives inductively the relationship of the exterior and interior angles of a convex polygon.					
9. illustrates a circle and the terms related to it: radius, diameter chord, center, arc, chord, central angles, and inscribed angles.	47.98	LM	62.00	MTM	-14.02
10. solve problems involving the sides and angles of a polygon					
Mean of Post-tests	54.37	LM	63.89	MTM	-9.52
Third Quarter Assessment	61.29	MTM	60.14	MTM	1.15

Legend: MPS – Mean Percentage Score, I – Interpretation, MD – Mean Difference
LM – Low Mastery MTM – Moving Towards Mastery M – Mastered

Table 8 above displays the mean percentage score of the different learning competencies in the weekly post-tests conducted on the control and experimental groups.

There is a significant increase in the MPS of the control and experimental groups. The students who learned math using the traditional method still have low mastery in the following competencies: (1) The learner represents point, line, and plane using concrete and pictorial models; (2) The learner illustrates subsets of a line; (3) The learner derives relationships of geometric figures using measurement and inductive reasoning: intersecting lines, perpendicular lines, parallel lines, and skew lines; (4) The learner derives relationships among angles formed by parallel lines cut by a transversal using measurement and inductive reasoning; (5) The learner illustrates polygons: (a) convexity, (b) angles, and (c) sides; (6) The learner derives inductively the relationship of the exterior and interior angles of a convex polygon; (7) The learner illustrates a circle and the terms related to it: radius, diameter chord, center, arc, chord, central angles, and inscribed angles; and (8) The learner solve problems involving the sides and angles of a polygon. Nevertheless, the same group of students who learned math using the traditional method moved towards mastery in the following competencies: (1) The learner classifies the different kinds of angles, and (2) The learner derives relationships of geometric figures using measurement and inductive reasoning: supplementary angles, complementary angles, congruent angles, vertical angles, adjacent angles, and linear pairs. Overall, the results of the third quarterly examination of the control group showed that students in the control group have moved towards mastery of the learning competencies in the entire third quarter with an MPS of 61.29.

On the other hand, the students who learned math with the aid of interactive video lessons still have low mastery in the following competencies: (1) The learner derives relationships of geometric figures using measurement and inductive reasoning: intersecting lines, perpendicular lines, parallel lines, and skew lines; (2) The learner derives relationships among angles formed by parallel lines cut by a transversal using measurement and inductive reasoning; (3) The learner illustrates polygons: (a) convexity, (b) angles, and (c) sides; and (4) The learner derives inductively the relationship of the exterior and interior angles of a convex polygon. Nevertheless, the same group of students who learned math using the interactive video lessons moved towards mastery in the following competencies: (1) The learner represents point, line, and plane using concrete and pictorial models; (2) The learner illustrates subsets of a line; (3) The learner classifies the different kinds of angles; (4) The learner derives relationships of geometric figures using measurement and inductive reasoning: supplementary angles, complementary angles, congruent angles, vertical angles, adjacent angles, and linear pairs; (5) The learner illustrates a circle and the terms related to it: radius, diameter chord, center, arc, chord, central angles and inscribed angles; and (6) The learner solve problems involving the sides and angles of a polygon. Overall, the results of the third quarterly examination of the experimental group showed that students have moved towards mastery of the learning competencies in the entire third quarter with an MPS of 60.14.

The MPS of the third quarterly examination of the control and experimental groups were 61.29 and 60.14, respectively. This result showed a higher MPS in the control group than in the experimental group, with a slight difference of 1.15, and the MPS were much closer. In the study of Olmos, O.L. & Lusung-Oyzon, M.P. (2008), note-taking and reviewing notes are related to better test scores. Furthermore, correlation tests showed high test scores are associated with more notes. In the event of the research, the researcher noted that students in the experimental group could not jot down notes of the discussion presented in the video lessons due to its continuous presentation. In contrast, the students in the control group could take down notes. This situation resulted in a lower MPS in the experimental group than in the control group.

The control group had the highest recorded MPS of 67.87 in the following learning competencies: (1) the learner classifies the different kinds of angles and (2) derives relationships of geometric figures using measurement and inductive reasoning: supplementary angles, complementary angles, congruent angles, vertical angles, adjacent angles, and linear pairs. On the other hand, the control group had the lowest recorded MPS of 41.91 in the following competencies: (1) illustrates polygons, (a) convexity, (b) angles, and (c) sides; and (2) derives inductively the relationship of the exterior and interior angles of a convex polygon.

The experimental group had the highest recorded MPS of 70.67 in the following competencies: (1) the learner represents point, line, and plane using concrete and pictorial models, and (2) the learner illustrates subsets of a line. On the other hand, the experimental group had the lowest recorded MPS of 58.79 in the following competencies: (1) derives relationships of geometric figures using measurement and inductive reasoning: intersecting lines, perpendicular lines, parallel lines, and skew lines, and (2) derives relationships among angles formed by parallel lines cut by a transversal using measurement and inductive reasoning.

These results indicate that video lessons effectively teach competencies about illustrating and representing geometrical figures. In contrast, the traditional way of teaching is more effective in teaching competencies about classifying and deriving relationships about geometrical figures.

2. Significant Difference in the Post-tests of the Control and Experimental Groups

The table below shows the independent sample test results between the post-tests of the control and experimental groups.

Table 9
Independent Samples Test Results Between the Post-tests of the Control and Experimental Groups

	MPS	MPS Difference	p-value	Description	Decision	
Post-test 1	Control	59.03	-11.64	<0.001	significant	Ho is rejected
	Experimental	70.67				
Post-test 2	Control	67.87	-0.98	0.811	not significant	Ho is not rejected
	Experimental	68.85				

Post-test 3	Control	55.04	-3.75	0.325	not significant	Ho is not rejected
	Experimental	58.79				
Post-test 4	Control	41.91	-17.21	<0.001	significant	Ho is rejected
	Experimental	59.12				
Post-test 5	Control	47.98	-14.02	0.652	not significant	Ho is not rejected
	Experimental	62.00				
Third Quarter Assessment	Control	61.29	1.15	0.197	not significant	Ho is not rejected
	Experimental	60.14				

Legend: MPS – Mean Percentage Score

Post-test 1 assesses the following competencies:

- The learner represents point, line, and plane using concrete and pictorial models
- The learner illustrates subsets of a line.

Post-test 2 assesses the following competencies:

- The learner classifies the different kinds of angles
- The learner derives relationships of geometric figures using measurement and inductive reasoning: supplementary angles, complementary angles, congruent angles, vertical angles, adjacent angles, and linear pairs

Post-test 3 assesses the following competencies:

- The learner derives relationships of geometric figures using measurement and inductive reasoning: intersecting lines, perpendicular lines, parallel lines, and skew lines
- The learner derives relationships among angles formed by parallel lines cut by a transversal using measurement and inductive reasoning.

Post-test 4 assesses the following competencies:

- The learner illustrates polygons: (a) convexity; (b) angles; and (c) sides.
- derives inductively the relationship of the exterior and interior angles of a convex polygon.

Post-test 5 assesses the following competencies:

- The learner illustrates a circle and the terms related to it: radius, diameter chord, center, arc, chord, central angles, and inscribed angles.
- The learner solves problems involving the sides and angles of a polygon

Table 9 compares the MPSs in the post-tests of the control and experimental groups. Between the two groups, the experimental group had the highest MPS from Post-test 1 to Post-test 5, while the control group had the highest MPS in the third quarterly assessment with a slight difference of 1.15. The MPS difference of Post-test 1 (-11.64), Post-test 4 (-17.21), and Post-test 5 (-14.02) had the highest MPS differences recorded. Among the three highest recorded MPS differences, only Post-test 1 (p-value is <0.001) and Post-test 4 (p-value is <0.001) are significantly different at 0.05 level of significance. Post-test 1 includes the following competencies: (1) represents point, line, and plane using concrete and pictorial models, (2) illustrates subsets of a line. Post-test four measures the following competencies: (3) illustrates polygons: (a) convexity, (b) angles, and (c) sides, and (4) derives inductively the relationship of the exterior and interior angles of a convex polygon. This result implies that using video lessons to teach the preceding competencies is more effective than the traditional way of teaching.

A similar finding by Jeremias and Carretero (2022) says that video lessons are practical in all classroom corners where educators can use them to create time and space for active learning. A developed and utilized video lesson improves the students' performance level in Mathematics. Furthermore, according to Insorio and Macandog (2022), a YouTube video playlist helps students understand and develop their mathematics competencies; watching the intervention boosts their confidence in answering the learning activities and performing tasks. Beltran (2021) asserted that integrating video lessons in teaching mathematics on the different Most Essential Learning Competencies could enhance the mathematics performance of Grade 5 pupils.

3. Academic Attributes of the Control and Experimental Groups towards Mathematics

The students' low achievement brings educators to the table to shed light on low achievement in Mathematics. Multiple factors, such as the teachers, the schools, and the students' attributes, affect the students' Mathematics achievement. Some student attributes are attitude, anxiety, motivation, and engagement. This research scrutinized these four attributes to define the level accordingly and statistically processed using mean, independent samples, and paired samples tests. The statistical results were summarized in Tables 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, and 16. These tables present the descriptive statistics of the level of attributes of Grade 7 students in terms of attitude, anxiety, motivation, and engagement before and after the third quarter of the school year 2023-2024. The level of students' academic attributes was analyzed to determine the effects of integrating video lessons in the said variables.

3.1. Students' Level of Attitude towards Mathematics in the Control and Experimental Groups

Attitude toward education is a well-known common factor in academic performance (Calalang, 2018). According to Yee (2010), attitude towards Mathematics is a positive or negative emotional disposition. Farooq et. Al. (2011), in a study of secondary school students in Pakistan, revealed no significant difference in the confidence of male and female students towards mathematics at the secondary level. They instead found that students' success in Mathematics depends on their attitude towards the subject.

Table 10
Students' Level of Attitude in Mathematics in the Control and Experimental Groups

Indicators	Control Group		Experimental Group	
	Before	After	Before	After
1. Mathematics is a very worthwhile and necessary subject.	4.46	4.61	4.12	4.69
2. Mathematics is enjoyable for me.	3.84	3.97	4.00	3.96
3. I get a great deal of satisfaction out of solving a mathematics problem.	3.86	3.89	3.63	4.25
4. Mathematics develops the mind and teaches a person to think.	3.94	4.31	3.98	4.63
5. Mathematics is important in everyday life.	4.51	4.69	4.36	4.44
6. Mathematics is one of the most important subjects for people to study.	4.35	4.37	4.32	4.63
7. High school math subjects would be very helpful no matter what I decide to study.	4.03	4.17	4.05	4.71
8. I can think of many ways where I can use math outside of school.	3.92	4.03	3.73	4.10
9. Mathematics is one of the subjects that I am most afraid of.	3.41	3.31	2.86	2.31
10. My mind goes blank and I am unable to think clearly when working on mathematics subject.	3.14	3.14	2.60	2.47
11. Studying mathematics makes me feel nervous.	2.70	2.89	2.81	2.48
12. Mathematics makes me feel uncomfortable.	3.42	3.57	3.20	3.65
13. I always feel significant stress in a mathematics class.	3.49	3.69	3.05	1.94
14. When I hear the word mathematics, I have a feeling of dislike.	3.59	3.83	3.53	4.10
15. It makes me nervous to even think about having to do a mathematics problem.	3.24	3.25	2.88	2.19
16. Mathematics does not scare me at all.	2.92	3.22	3.29	2.98
17. I have a lot of self-confidence when it comes to mathematics.	3.31	3.42	3.30	3.46
18. I can solve mathematics problems without too much difficulty.	3.14	3.14	3.25	2.90
19. I expect to do fairly well in any math class I take.	3.06	3.25	3.57	3.15

20.	I am always confused in my mathematics class.	2.86	2.89	2.70	2.53
21.	I feel a sense of insecurity when trying to do mathematics activities.	3.14	3.11	2.67	2.10
22.	I learn mathematics easily.	3.14	3.31	3.34	3.04
23.	I feel confident when working on math problems.	3.38	3.51	3.65	3.48
24.	I have usually enjoyed studying mathematics in school.	3.73	3.81	3.79	3.91
25.	Mathematics is dull and boring.	4.00	3.83	3.66	4.65
26.	I like to solve new problems in mathematics.	3.49	3.69	3.60	3.60
27.	I would prefer to do an assignment in math than to write an essay.	3.35	3.28	3.38	3.40
28.	I would like to avoid mathematics subjects in the next grade levels.	3.43	3.42	2.95	4.46
29.	I really like mathematics.	3.51	3.69	3.80	4.17
30.	I am happier in a Mathematics class than in any other subject.	3.00	3.14	3.57	3.29
31.	Mathematics is a very interesting subject.	3.81	3.89	3.91	4.13
32.	I am willing to do more than the required amount of time in mathematics.	3.25	3.33	3.70	3.06
33.	If given a chance, I plan to take more mathematics subjects than the other.	3.05	3.14	3.39	2.96
34.	I find the challenge in mathematics interesting.	3.51	3.75	3.81	3.81
35.	I think studying advanced mathematics is useful.	4.03	4.06	4.05	4.40
36.	I believe studying math helps me with problem-solving in other areas.	3.97	3.86	4.12	4.42
37.	I am comfortable expressing my ideas on how to look for solutions to a difficult problem in math.	3.41	3.50	3.95	3.42
38.	I am comfortable answering questions in math class.	3.49	3.57	3.73	3.73
39.	A strong math background could help me in my future studies.	4.05	4.31	4.07	4.79
40.	I believe I am good at solving math problems.	3.22	3.36	3.59	3.46
Grand Mean		3.53	3.63	3.55	3.60
Interpretation		MP	MP	MP	MP

Note: All responses to negative statements are recorded as follows: 1 – Highly Positive, 2 – Moderately Positive, 3 – Positive, 4 – Negative, and 5 – Extremely Negative

Legend:

	Interpretation	Range of Means			
HP	Highly Positive	4.21 – 5.00	P	Positive	2.61 – 3.40
MP	Moderately Positive	3.41 – 4.20	N	Negative	1.81 – 2.60
			EN	Extremely Negative	1.00 – 1.80

Table 10 revealed the students' attitudes towards Mathematics in the control and experimental groups. It shows a moderately positive attitude of the students in the control and experimental groups before the start of the third quarter; the control group has a grand mean of 3.53 (moderately positive), and the experimental group has a grand mean of 3.55 (moderately positive). At the end of the third quarter, the student's level of attitude was 3.63 (moderately positive) for the control group and 3.60 (moderately positive) for the experimental group. Based on the results, the control and experimental groups improved the students' attitudes but are still categorically described as having a moderately positive attitude. The same results on the control and experimental groups manifest that traditional or video-based teaching may at least improve students' attitudes towards Mathematics but not significantly high.

Based on the presented table 10, the following indicators exhibited the highly positive attitude of the students in the control group at the end of the experiment: Mathematics is a very worthwhile and necessary subject (mean = 4.61, highly positive); Mathematics develops the mind and teaches a person to think (mean = 4.31, highly positive); Mathematics is important in everyday life (mean = 4.69, highly positive); Mathematics is one of the most important subjects for people to study (mean = 4.37, highly positive); A strong math background could help me in my future studies (mean = 4.31, highly positive).

While, the following indicators exhibited the highly positive attitude of the students in the experimental group at the end of the experiment: Mathematics is a very worthwhile and necessary subject (mean = 4.69, highly positive); I get a great deal of satisfaction out of solving a mathematics problem (mean = 4.25, highly positive); Mathematics develops the mind and teaches a person to think (mean = 4.63, highly positive); Mathematics is important in everyday life (mean = 4.44, highly positive); Mathematics is one of the most important subjects for people to study (mean = 4.63, highly positive); High school math subjects would be very helpful no matter what I decide to study (mean = 4.71, highly positive); Mathematics is dull and boring (mean = 4.65, highly positive); I would like to avoid mathematics subjects in the next grade levels (mean = 4.46, highly positive); I think studying advanced mathematics is useful (mean = 4.40, highly positive); I believe studying math helps me with problem solving in other areas (mean = 4.42, highly positive); and A strong math background could help me in my future studies (mean = 4.79, highly positive).

Among the forty (40) indicators that measured the students' attitudes, five (5) in the control group showed a highly positive attitude. In comparison, eleven (11) indicators in the experimental group indicated a highly positive attitude.

3.2. Students' Level of Anxiety in Mathematics in the Control and Experimental Groups

Mathematics anxiety can be a negative emotional response to mathematics that significantly impairs the ability to carry out mathematical tasks. Anxiety can lead to stress and avoidance behaviors, inhibit individuals' performance, and hinder their abilities (Carey et al., 2019; O'Leary et al., 2017).

Table 11
Students' Level of Anxiety in Mathematics in the Control and Experimental Groups

Indicators	Control Group		Experimental Group	
	Before	After	Before	After
1. Having a fast heartbeat during Math class	3.00	2.69	3.20	3.67
2. Having a heavy head feeling during Math class	2.24	2.06	2.86	3.30
3. Feeling like about to faint	1.89	1.75	2.75	1.45
4. A more frequent breathing activity	2.11	2.06	2.89	2.26
5. Feeling hard to breathe	1.73	1.69	2.25	1.54
6. Experiencing tension in the facial muscles	1.54	1.44	2.34	1.85
7. Having a stomachache/twisted stomach	1.77	1.67	2.12	1.90
8. Difficulty in swallowing	1.59	1.53	2.40	1.44
9. Blushing face whenever I am the center of attention in class	2.08	2.28	3.16	2.50
10. Sudden sweaty hands	2.95	3.03	2.95	3.42
11. Cold sweats	2.00	2.19	2.67	2.25
12. Having muscle ache	1.62	1.61	2.23	1.67
13. Walking back and forth in the classroom	1.76	1.61	2.42	1.79
14. Often asking for permission to use the restroom	2.59	2.61	3.57	3.10
15. Having a habit of teething teeth or biting anything like nails, hands, hair, etc.	2.46	2.28	2.55	2.04
16. Having an unstable voice whenever the teacher asks to recite	3.03	2.97	3.11	2.56
17. Having shocked reaction whenever called out	3.43	3.33	3.36	3.29

18. Talking fast or nervously during recitation	2.86	3.08	3.20	3.27
19. Experiencing disrupted or restless sleep	2.06	2.42	2.98	3.06
20. Easy to lose concentration	2.53	2.49	3.09	3.42
21. I like to avoid problems.	2.86	2.77	2.95	2.56
22. Tend to be excessively alert in class	2.81	2.57	3.05	3.19
23. Tend to cheat when facing difficult problems	2.05	2.00	2.20	2.19
24. Often determining the wrong answer	3.08	3.00	2.79	3.56
25. Often feeling confused during math tests	2.77	2.80	3.09	3.47
26. Suddenly forget the lesson when under time pressure	3.08	3.18	3.34	3.94
27. After the exam, still felt guilty about the answer	3.08	3.00	4.00	4.38
28. Worrying about something bad to happen	3.00	2.83	3.61	3.54
29. Feeling ashamed of other people asking about mathematical materials	2.78	2.64	3.29	2.67
30. Feeling confused when facing math problems alone	3.14	3.22	3.23	3.40
31. Feeling afraid of the result of the test	3.70	3.69	4.02	4.43
32. Feeling more afraid to face the mathematics test rather than the other subjects	3.32	3.36	3.66	3.17
General Mean	2.53	2.50	2.98	2.82
Interpretation	Low	Low	High	High

Legend:

<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Range of Means</i>
<i>Very High</i>	4.21 – 5.00
<i>Moderately High</i>	3.41 – 4.20
<i>High</i>	2.61 – 3.40
<i>Low</i>	1.81 – 2.60
<i>Very Low</i>	1.00 – 1.80

Table 11 displays the students' level of anxiety in Mathematics at the beginning and end of the third quarter. The control group initially had a low level of anxiety with a mean of 2.53, which somewhat improved to a mean of 2.50, but was still on a low level of anxiety. The experimental group initially had a high level of anxiety with a mean of 2.98, which also improved to a mean of 2.82, but still on the level of high anxiety.

3.3. Students' Level of Motivation in Mathematics in the Control and Experimental Groups

Students' Academic motivation strengthens the direction of goals and learner interest, especially in mathematics. However, the students' educational problems include complaints that mathematics is complex, a lack of motivation and study habits, strict teachers, and low performance in significant examinations (Laguador, 2013).

Table 12
Students Level of Motivation in Mathematics in the Control and Experimental Groups

Indicators	Control Group		Experimental Group	
	Before	After	Before	After
1. I sleep late so I can finish my projects in Math.	3.03	3.06	3.68	3.75
2. I study hard enough to understand Mathematics better.	3.57	3.64	4.14	4.08
3. I do thorough research for my projects.	3.54	3.31	3.84	3.62
4. I devote most of my time to doing my assignments.	2.97	2.89	3.80	4.19
5. I find other resources when I am doing a project.	3.42	3.56	3.68	3.25
6. I come to school earlier so that I will get more schoolwork done and be able to understand the lessons more.	3.51	3.67	4.05	3.96
7. I like to study during my free time in school.	3.38	3.42	3.61	2.98
8. I push myself to do better.	3.97	3.86	4.11	4.42

9. I am at my best when the activity or lesson is challenging.	3.44	3.64	3.70	4.19
10. I tend to work harder whenever I receive criticism.	3.54	3.56	3.63	4.21
11. I perform better when I am with a group.	3.49	3.61	4.02	3.85
12. I always had passing remarks because I am expected to be one.	3.38	3.36	3.37	4.25
13. I go to school simply because I want to please my parents.	2.35	2.36	3.07	1.54
14. I need to do my best for the people around me to see that I am an excellent student.	3.69	3.78	3.95	3.88
15. I work better when I have my friends around.	3.36	3.54	3.70	3.54
16. I feel happy when I receive praise from my classmates.	3.95	3.97	4.02	4.38
17. I feel happy when I receive praise from my teachers.	3.97	4.19	4.16	4.71
18. I invest extra effort in school so that I will be acknowledged.	3.69	3.78	3.66	3.58
19. I push myself to do better in the group.	3.62	3.67	4.07	4.23
20. I perform better when my group sees my efforts.	3.54	3.64	3.88	4.35
21. I focused on my studies better so that I could pass this grade level.	4.41	4.33	4.36	4.58
22. I work hard on the topic given to me because I know it will have positive results.	3.78	3.94	4.02	4.10
23. I make sure to make my projects extra special so that I will get a higher grade.	3.84	3.94	4.09	4.23
24. I work harder to receive an exemption for the next examination.	3.69	3.71	3.93	4.29
25. I do things at my best because I will receive a reward from my parents.	3.19	3.11	3.63	3.75
26. I practice my communication skills to be more proficient and fluent.	3.54	3.78	3.77	3.98
27. I put extra effort into my outputs to receive additional points.	3.95	4.03	4.05	4.35
28. I do thorough research for my assignment to make sure I will have a high grade for it.	3.54	3.69	3.60	3.50
29. I read my lessons in advance before going to school to get a perfect score in recitations.	3.54	3.69	3.63	3.38
30. I always give my 100% in every homework so that I can get a perfect score.	3.51	3.61	3.64	4.13
General Mean	3.55	3.61	3.83	3.91
Interpretation	MP	MP	MP	MP

Legend:

	Interpretation	Range of Means
HP	Highly Positive	4.21 – 5.00
MP	Moderately Positive	3.41 – 4.20
P	Positive	2.61 – 3.40
N	Negative	1.81 – 2.60
EN	Extremely Negative	1.00 – 1.80

Reflected in Table 12 is the level of academic motivation of the students in learning mathematics. At the beginning of the third quarter, the control group had an overall mean score of 3.55, with a descriptive interpretation of moderately positive. In contrast, at the end of the third quarter, the control group had an overall mean score of 3.61, with the same descriptive interpretation of moderately positive. The mean difference in the level of academic motivation in the control group before and after the third quarter is 0.06, suggesting an improvement in the student's academic motivation in the control group.

Table 12 also contained the students' academic motivation level in the experimental group. At the beginning of the third quarter, the experimental group had an overall mean score of 3.83, with a descriptive interpretation of moderately positive. In contrast, at the end of the third quarter, the experimental group had an overall mean score of 3.91, with the same descriptive interpretation of moderately positive. The mean difference in the level of academic motivation in the experimental group before and after the third quarter is 0.08, which suggests that there is also an improvement in the student's academic motivation when video lessons are integrated into the teaching process.

The following statements are indicators labeled as highly positive motivations of students from the experimental group: I push myself to do better (mean - 4.42); I tend to work harder whenever I receive criticisms (mean - 4.21); I always had passing remarks because I am expected to be one (mean - 4.25); I feel happy when I receive praises from my classmates (mean - 4.38); I feel happy when I receive praises from my teachers (mean - 4.71); I push myself to do better in group (mean - 4.23); I perform better when my group sees my efforts (mean - 4.35); I focus on my studies better so that I could pass this grade level (mean - 4.58); I make sure to make my projects extra special so that I will get a higher grade (mean - 4.23); I work harder to receive an exemption to the next examination (mean - 4.29); and I put extra efforts in my outputs to receive additional points (mean - 4.35).

Among the thirty (30) indicators that measured the level of motivation of the students, eleven (11) indicators in the experimental group showed a highly positive motivation, fifteen (15) indicators showed a moderately positive motivation, three (3) indicators were positive, and one (1) showed an extremely negative motivation among students in the experimental group. In the control group, one (1) indicator indicates a highly positive motivation, twenty-three (23) were moderately positive indicators, five (5) were positive, and one (1) indicator was labeled as a negative motivation among students in the control group. Comparing the two groups, the experimental group demonstrates the highest frequency in the highly positive motivation category. The results indicate that integrating video lessons in teaching promotes a more highly positive motivation among students than the usual method of teaching (traditional method).

3.4. Students' Level of Engagement in Mathematics in the Control and Experimental Groups

Academic engagement refers to the quality and quantity of students' participation or connection with the educational endeavor and, hence, with activities, values, individuals, aims, and places that comprise it. According to Joshi et al. (2022), a meaningful engagement of learners is critical in the quality teaching and learning of mathematics at the school level.

Table 13
Students' Level of Engagement in Mathematics in the Control and Experimental Groups

Indicators	Control Group		Experimental Group	
	Before	After	Before	After
1. I use information from math class to complete homework assignments.	4.14	4.22	4.36	4.57
2. In the math class I am taking this quarter, I feel that my teacher creates an encouraging learning environment.	3.89	3.94	3.93	4.34
3. The Mathematics class I have taken so far met my expectations about what I thought high school would be like.	3.78	3.92	3.86	4.15
4. What I am learning now in math class will help me in the future.	4.17	4.38	4.33	4.53
5. When I have questions regarding classwork in math, I visit the faculty during office hours.	2.49	2.44	3.07	3.48

6.	Even when I do NOT have questions about classwork in math, I visit the faculty during office hours.	2.24	2.25	2.88	3.24
7.	I feel comfortable approaching my math teacher with questions regarding classwork.	3.43	3.64	3.95	3.85
8.	I feel comfortable asking my math teacher to clarify lesson information.	3.62	3.75	4.00	3.70
9.	I feel that my teacher professionally interacts with me.	3.32	3.39	3.91	4.11
10.	Meeting with my math teacher helps me to do well in class.	3.57	3.66	4.00	4.43
11.	Meeting with my teacher helps me to solidify my future academic goals.	3.35	3.42	3.79	4.18
12.	Positive experiences with staff (people at the library, admissions, etc.) will motivate me to seek additional help in the future.	3.40	3.49	3.93	3.89
13.	I meet with my classmates outside of class, at school, to study together.	3.38	3.46	3.77	3.61
14.	I meet with my classmates outside of class, at school, to socialize.	3.46	3.17	3.71	3.72
15.	I meet with my classmates off school to study.	3.22	3.22	3.56	2.59
16.	I meet with my classmates off school to socialize.	2.97	3.14	3.33	3.45
17.	I enjoy working on group projects outside of class.	3.41	3.51	3.88	4.04
18.	Meeting with my classmates makes attending Mathematics more enjoyable.	3.81	3.71	3.98	4.00
19.	Meeting with my classmates helps me to feel less alone as a student.	3.71	3.50	3.63	4.11
20.	I think about meeting with my classmates to complete class assignments.	3.53	3.37	3.49	3.00
21.	When I have good experiences with my classmates, I am more motivated to work with others in future classes.	3.44	3.56	3.84	4.28
22.	I believe that working with other students with different cultural backgrounds will be beneficial.	3.24	3.24	3.66	3.80
23.	I am involved in a campus club, organization, and/or recreational activity, such as the associated student body, a mathematics club, and/or intramural sports.	2.43	2.14	3.71	3.46
24.	I am involved in organizing events and activities in school.	2.61	2.64	3.76	3.82
25.	I attend campus events and/or activities even if I am not a member of the club or organization hosting the event.	2.63	2.69	3.55	3.62
26.	I feel like an important member of a campus club, organization, and/or recreational activity.	2.49	2.46	3.57	3.6
27.	It is important for me to feel integrated into campus organizations and clubs.	2.71	2.58	3.69	3.6
28.	I think that being involved in campus clubs, organizations, and/or recreational activities will make me a more well-rounded student.	2.83	2.78	3.64	3.65
29.	Participating in campus clubs, organizations, and/or recreational activities has exposed me to a variety of new and interesting cultures and ideas.	3.00	2.92	3.90	3.82
30.	I admire my surroundings when I walk through the school.	3.47	3.31	4.00	4.38
31.	I feel safe when I am in school.	4.32	4.17	4.02	3.89
32.	I look forward to coming to school.	3.95	3.97	3.98	4.39
33.	I feel that this school is accommodating the needs of all students.	3.76	3.82	4.32	4.13
34.	I think that the library has good print resources available for my use.	4.16	4.03	4.38	4.22
35.	The computer labs on campus are important for me to do my homework or complete assignments for my classes.	3.68	3.66	3.84	4.40
General Mean		3.36	3.36	3.81	3.95
Interpretation		P	P	MP	MP

Legend:

<i>HP</i>	Interpretation <i>Highly Positive</i>	Range of Means 4.21 – 5.00
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MP	Moderately Positive	3.41 – 4.20
P	Positive	2.61 – 3.40
N	Negative	1.81 – 2.60
EN	Extremely Negative	1.00 – 1.80

Table 13 shows the student's level of engagement in mathematics of the control and experimental groups. Data revealed that at the beginning and the end of the third quarter, the control group had the same overall mean score of 3.36 with a positive descriptive interpretation. There is no mean difference in the level of academic engagement in the control group before and after the third quarter, suggesting no improvement in the student's academic engagement in the control group.

Table 13 also contained the students' academic engagement level in the experimental group. At the beginning of the third quarter, the experimental group had an overall mean score of 3.81 with a descriptive interpretation of moderately positive, while ending the third quarter, the experimental group had an overall mean score of 3.95 with the same descriptive interpretation of moderately positive. The mean difference in the level of academic engagement in the experimental group before and after the third quarter is 0.14, which suggests that there is an improvement in the academic engagement of the students when video lessons are integrated into the teaching process.

Among the thirty-five (35) indicators that measured the level of engagement of the students, nine (9) indicators in the experimental group showed a highly positive engagement, twenty-three (23) indicators showed a moderately positive engagement, two (2) indicators were positive, and one (1) showed a negative engagement among students in the experimental group. In the control group, two (2) indicators indicated a highly positive engagement, seventeen (17) were moderately positive indicators, eleven (11) were positive, and five (5) indicators indicated negative engagement among students in the control group. Comparing the two groups, the experimental group demonstrates the highest frequency in the highly positive and moderately positive engagement categories. The results indicate that integrating video lessons in teaching promotes a more highly positive engagement among students than the usual method of teaching (traditional method).

4. Significant Difference in the Academic Attributes of the Control and Experimental Groups

The succeeding tables show the inferential statistics on the significant difference between the academic attributes of the control and experimental groups at a 0.05 significance level.

Table 14
Independent Samples Test Results in the Post-assessments of the Level of Students' Attributes

Attributes	Mean	Mean Difference	p-value	Description	Decision
Attitude	Control	3.63	0.03	0.712	not significant
	Experimental	3.60			
Anxiety	Control	2.50	-0.32	0.003	significant

	Experimental	2.82				
Motivation	Control	3.61	-0.30	0.002	significant	Ho is rejected
	Experimental	3.91				
Engagement	Control	3.36	-0.59	<0.001	significant	Ho is rejected
	Experimental	3.95				

Table 14 shows the test results of the independent samples of the post-assessments of the different attributes of the students in the control and experimental groups. The data revealed no significant difference in the attitude of the students in the control and experimental groups ($p = 0.712, > 0.05$). This result indicates that either traditional method or video-based teaching may guarantee an improved attitude of students towards Mathematics.

While concerning the level of anxiety, Table 14 revealed that there is a significant difference in the anxiety level of the students in the control and experimental groups ($p = 0.003, < 0.05$). The level of motivation of the control and experimental groups showed the same result, where the post-assessments of the two groups were statistically different ($p = 0.002$) at a 0.05 level of significance. As for the level of engagement, the results were the same, where post-assessments between the two groups were statistically different. This information implies that using video lessons in teaching made a more significant change or improvement to the anxiety, motivation, and engagement of the students than just using the traditional teaching method.

Table 15

Paired Samples Test Results of Pre-and Post-assessments of the Control Group

Attributes	t-value	p-value	Description	Decision
Attitude	-2.339	0.125	not significant	Ho is not rejected
Anxiety	1.096	0.281	not significant	Ho is not rejected
Motivation	-1.384	0.175	not significant	Ho is not rejected
Engagement	-0.066	0.948	not significant	Ho is not rejected

Reflected in Table 15 are the paired sample test results of the pre-and post-assessments of the different attributes of the students in the control group, where the teacher used traditional teaching. Data revealed that the different attributes are not statistically significant: attitude ($t_{35} = 0.125, p > 0.05$); anxiety ($t_{35} = 0.281, p > 0.05$); motivation ($t_{35} = 0.175, p > 0.05$); and engagement ($t_{35} = 0.948, p > 0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis (H_1 : There is no significant difference between the pre-assessment and post-assessment of the control group) is true and accepted. These results further imply that using the traditional way of teaching did not show a significant improvement in the attributes of the students.

Table 16

Paired Samples Test Results of Pre-and Post-assessments of the Experimental Group

Attributes	t-value	p-value	Description	Decision
Attitude	-0.675	0.504	not significant	Ho is not rejected
Anxiety	1.769	0.083	not significant	Ho is not rejected
Motivation	-1.420	0.163	not significant	Ho is not rejected
Engagement	-1.587	0.120	not significant	Ho is not rejected

Table 16 shows the paired sample test results of the pre- and post-assessments of the different attributes of the students in the experimental group where the teacher integrated video lessons into teaching. Data revealed that the different attributes are not statistically significant: attitude ($t_{42} = 0.504, p > 0.05$); anxiety ($t_{47} = 0.083, p > 0.05$); motivation ($t_{42} = 0.163, p > 0.05$); and engagement ($t_{41} = 0.120, p > 0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis (H1: There is no significant difference between the pre-assessment and post-assessment of the experimental group) is true and accepted. This result further implies that integrating video lessons into teaching did not significantly improve the students' attributes at the experiment's beginning and end. The researcher suggested that additional studies explore the long-term effects of video lessons on the students' attributes since there was a significant improvement in the attributes in comparison to the traditional way of teaching (refer to Table 14).

Proposed Video-based Teaching Package based on the Findings of the Study

The study aimed to assess the effects of utilizing video lessons in teaching mathematics to seventh-grade students. The findings revealed significant improvements in students' academic performance, particularly in competencies related to representing and illustrating geometric figures. Furthermore, the video lessons were found to be highly effective in reducing student anxiety levels while simultaneously enhancing engagement and motivation within the classroom. These results underscore the potential of incorporating video-based teaching methodologies to enhance the learning experience and outcomes for students in mathematics education.

A video-based teaching package, comprising video lessons and accompanying lesson exemplars was developed and implemented. The video-based teaching package may be accessed through this link <https://tinyurl.com/VBTP-JonalynMendeja>. The video-based teaching package covers the following topics and competencies (refer to Table 17) where video lessons are found to be more effective than traditional method of teaching.

Table 17
Topics and Competencies Covered in the Video-based Teaching Package

Topics	Learning Competencies
1. Point, Line and Plane	represents point, line, and plane using concrete and pictorial models
2. Other Terms in Geometry	represents point, line, and plane using concrete and pictorial models
3. Subsets of a Line	illustrates subsets of a line
4. Polygons	illustrates polygons: (a) convexity, (b) angles, and (c) sides
5. Exterior and Interior Angles of a Convex Polygon	derives inductively the relationship of the exterior and interior angles of a convex polygon.

Conclusions

This study determines the effects of using video lessons on the academic performance and academic attributes (attitude, anxiety, motivation, and engagement) of grade 7 students in Mathematics. The results showed that:

1.1. Academic Performance: The experimental group, exposed to video lessons, showed higher mean percentage scores (MPS) in post-tests than the control group. Notably, the experimental group demonstrated improvement in various competencies. Video lessons were more effective for competencies related to representing/illustrating geometric figures.

1.2. Attitude: Both groups displayed a moderately positive attitude toward Mathematics, with the experimental group showing slightly higher mean scores. The experimental group had more highly positive attitude indicators than the control. There is no significant difference in the students' attitudes before and after the duration of the study, both in the control and experimental groups. At the end of the study, there is no significant difference in the student's attitudes in the control and experimental groups.

1.3. Anxiety: There is no significant difference in the anxiety of the students before and after the study's duration in both control and experimental groups. However, there is a significant difference in the students' anxiety in the control and experimental groups at the end of the study.

1.4. Motivation: Both groups were moderately motivated initially and after the intervention. The experimental group exhibited higher motivation levels since the experimental group had more indicators of highly positive motivation than the control. There is no significant difference in the student's motivation before and after the duration of the study, both in the control and experimental groups. However, there is a significant difference in the student's motivation in the control and experimental groups at the end of the study.

1.5. Engagement: The control group's engagement level did not change. The experimental group showed improvement in engagement level. There is no significant difference in the student's engagement before and after the duration of the study, both in the control and experimental groups. However, there is a significant difference in the student's engagement in the control and experimental groups at the end of the study.

The research findings indicate that employing video lessons in teaching mathematics positively and negatively impacts student learning outcomes. Video lessons positively impacted academic performance, leading to higher MPS in the experimental group. Video lessons can enhance academic performance, especially for representing/illustrating geometric concepts. In conclusion, video lessons seemed to enhance students' academic performance in mathematics more effectively than traditional teaching methods. However, the lack of note-taking ability during the video

lessons may have contributed to the slightly lower performance of the experimental group on the final assessment.

Video lessons enhance student anxiety, engagement, motivation, and understanding of mathematical concepts. The study also highlights that video-based teaching can improve students' anxiety, motivation, and engagement levels compared to traditional teaching methods. Video lessons enhanced motivation levels, indicating a potential benefit in student engagement. Students exposed to video lessons demonstrated improved engagement, suggesting the effectiveness of this teaching method. Both methods (video-based and traditional) may contribute to fostering a positive attitude towards Mathematics, but not significantly.

Recommendations

Based on the effects that video lessons have on students' academic performance and attributes, the researcher recommends the following:

1. **Implementation of Video Lessons:** Continue integrating video lessons in Mathematics classes to enhance academic performance and motivation. Moreover, incorporating video lessons is advantageous alongside traditional teaching methods, especially for visual/concrete representations.
2. **Focus on Engagement:** Emphasize strategies to improve student engagement further, building on the positive impact observed.
3. **Further Research:** Conduct additional studies to investigate the long-term impacts of video lessons on academic performance and student attitudes. Further, conduct follow-up studies with larger sample sizes across different grade levels/subjects.
4. **Explore integrating video lessons with other technology-based interventions for a more comprehensive approach.**
5. **Adopt the researcher-made video lessons especially the lessons for representing/ illustrating geometric concepts. Prior to the adoption of the researcher-made video lessons, it should be subjected for review by experts.**

These findings highlight the potential of video lessons in improving academic outcomes and student motivation, providing valuable insights for future educational practices.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers declare that this study was conducted in full compliance with ethical standards. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to their participation, ensuring that they were fully aware of the study's nature and their involvement. Respondents were given the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. The anonymity of the respondents was rigorously maintained to protect their privacy, and their well-being was a priority throughout the research

process. The authors affirm that no conflicts of interest were present in the conduct of the study. All efforts were made to avoid plagiarism, ensuring that the work is original and properly attributed. The interpretation of the findings was conducted impartially, without any bias, and the results are intended solely for research purposes.

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- ***The Researcher***

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